

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B033
 Date: 22 Jul 2004
 Take Off: 10:51:13
 Landing: 16:01:26
 Flight Time: 5h10m13

Trials Instructions: ITOP – Interception of North American pollution, characterisation of background atmosphere and ENVISAT validation.

Operating Area: West of Azores

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	Mission Scientist 1	Steve Arnold	Leeds University
4	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM
5	Core Chemistry/FWVS/CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
6	HCHO	Graham Mills	UEA
7	PTR-MS	Anne Hulse	UEA
8	WAS	Nicola Watson	York University
9	PERCA	Alex Parker	Leicester University
10	Peroxides	Brian Bandy	UEA
11	AMS	Paul Williams	UMIST
12	NOxy	Dave Stewart	UEA
13	Mission Scientist 2	John Methven	Reading University
14	Mission Scientist 3	Ally Lewis	York University
15	PAN/TDL	James Lee	York University
16	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
17			
18			

Flight Track:

Flight B033 Latest 22/07/04 1600Z 28.66W 38.50N 1046 ft

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B033
 Date: 22/07/2004
 Project: ITOP
 Location: Horta, Azores

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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104437		Taxi			PSAP flow off
105113		T/O	0.00 kft	270	
105518	105756	Run 1	5.0 kft	338	
105750					JW calcs complete
105916		EVM	6.0 kft	298	PSAP flow on
110329	120257	Run 2	10.0 kft	299	
111829		EVM	10.0 kft	300	PSAP rack not on, now powered up
112210		EVM	10.0 kft	301	NOxy cal complete
113900					start video recording
115800					SATCOM call, CCM to DFL
120440	122231	Profile 1	10.0 - 26.0 kft	298	
122342	125011	Run 3	26.0 kft	290	
122631		EVM	26.0 kft	289	Core Chem cal finishd
122735					TWC reset
125218	130943	Profile 2.1	26.0 - 5.0 kft	207	2500 ft/min
130000					SATCOM call, CCM to DFL
130007		interrupt P 2.1	15.5 kft	205	
130205		recommence P 2.1	15.5 kft	013	
131728	132724	Profile 2.2	5.0 - 0.10 kft	200	500 ft/min
132200		EVM			ship plume?
132921	133922	Run 4	0.10 kft	089	
133929	134425	Profile 3	0.10 - 3.0 kft	075	
134119					PSAP flow off
134302		EVM	1.8 kft	080	cloud line
134529	135530	Run 5	3.0 kft	076	
134620					PSAP flow on
135552	140056	Profile 4.1	3.0 - 5.0 kft	078	500 ft min
140056	140714	Profile 4.2	5.0 - 11.0 kft	079	1000ft/min
140730	141731	Run 6	11.0 kft	079	
141917	142437	Profile 5	11.0 - 16.0 kft	282	
142447	143420	Run 7	16.0 kft	275	
143420	143932	Profile 6	16.0 - 21.0 kft	274	
144153	145154	Run 8	21.0 kft	088	
145154	150211	Profile 7	21.0 - 9.1 kft	089	
150331	154534	Run 9	9.0 kft	098	
150802		EVM	9.0 kft	095	Core Chem cal finishd
152151		EVM	9.0 kft	096	NOxy cal finished
160000					PSAP flow off
160126		Land	0.09 kft	270	
160525	GPS final	position 38.31.26N	28 42.98W		
160600	INU final	position 38 30.70N	28 41.93W		

B033 Track 22-JUL-04

39°W 37°W 35°W 33°W 31°W 29°W 27°W

41°N

40°N

39°N

38°N

37°N

41°N

40°N

39°N

38°N

37°N

39°W 37°W 35°W 33°W 31°W 29°W 27°W

A 2488

NAT TRACKS TO LISBON AIRPORT
 NAT tracks are anchored on Espichel VORTAC and Santiago VORDME, tributary tracks via DIRMA Int will be cleared. All operators conducting flight operations in the Santa Maria OCA north of 37°N shall provide information to Santa Maria OAC regarding the tracks likely to be requested during the peak traffic periods.

② Traffic intending to cross the EUR/SAM RVSM corridor should insert the entry/exit points and the respective estimated crossing times as well as for the crossing of each of the fixed ATS routes into the FPL item 18.

① RNAV - REQUIRED NAVIGATIONAL PERFORMANCE 10NM (RNP10) & MACH NUMBER TECHNIQUE
 For details about RNP 10 refer to ATC page 551 and following. The Mach Number Technique is based on the true Mach No. The ATC clearance must include the assigned Mach No. which is to be maintained. It is therefore necessary that information on the desired Mach No. at the Entry/Exit points has to be stated in the flight plan by pilots intending to operate jet aircraft along the following ATS routes:

- UN 741	NELSO	(N31 41.0 W017 27.4)	- Fortaleza VORDME
- UN 873	LIMAL	(N25 00.0 W017 37.5)	- Natal VORDME
- UN 866	APASO	(N25 00.0 W019 30.3)	- Mossoro VORDME
- UN 857	BIPET	(N25 00.0 W016 21.5)	- Noronha VORDME
- UB 623	LIMAL	(N25 00.0 W017 37.5)	- Noronha VORDME

It is imperative that pilots adhere strictly to their assigned Mach numbers unless a specific reclearance is obtained from the appropriate ATC unit. If an immediate temporary change in the Mach number is required due to turbulence, ATC must be notified as soon as possible.

RNAV required in all European upper airspace. Should aircraft not be RNAV equipped/nor operational, include a "Negative-RNAV" report immediately after the aircraft call sign on initial contact on an ATC frequency.

NAT MNPS (FL 285-FL 42)

B033: ITOP – Interception of North American pollution, characterisation of background atmosphere and ENVISAT validation.

Mission Scientists: Steve Arnold & John Methven

Date: 22/07/04

Outline schedule:

07:00 UT - Power to aircraft - Warm-up

09:00 UT - Air Crew Briefing

10:15 UT – Security sweep

10:30 UT – Boarding deadline

11:00 UT - Take-off

Location: West of Azores

Aim: To intercept a layer of polluted air near Azores at around FL100, which is due to pass over France on 24-25/07/04. Profiles through the depth of the operating region will be made to characterise air above and below polluted layers. A stepped deep profile in the west of the operating region will be made to coincide with the location and time of an ENVISAT overpass between 13:01 and 13:02 UT.

Sortie Detail

1. T+0 Take Off. Ascend to first available level for wet chemistry checks. (10)
2. T+10 Ascend to FL100 and transit directly to edge of operating region (34W) via Koker. Include at least 20 mins level in clear air for calcs. (65)
3. T+75 Profile ascend to FL260 into satellite swath (20).
4. T+95 Continue on same heading further into satellite swath looking for cloud-free region. (15)
5. T+110 Turn southwards and profile descend to 100ft (@ 1500 ft/min) in stepped pattern along swath of satellite pass (@13:01:30) (20)
6. T +130 Turn onto heading for route to Koker. Level run @ 100ft (20).
7. T+150 Profile ascent to FL260 (1000 ft/min), interrupted by level runs of 10 mins each on two levels to be determined in flight. (45)
8. T+195 Profile descend to FL110 for exit via Koker. (20)
9. T+215 Leave operating region and transit back to Horta. (75)
10. T+290 Land.

Flight B033 22nd July 2004 Report

The aims of the flight were: a) to intercept a layer of polluted air of North American origin, which the forecast showed to be lying almost directly overhead Horta, stretching out to the west, and which was forecast to be advected onto France in subsequent days; b) to characterise the background chemical profile of the North Atlantic outside of the layers of pollution, which had been ubiquitous in ITOP flights to date; c) to make a deep profile descent coincident with the position and time of an ENVISAT overpass between 13:01 and 13:02 UT.

The submitted flight plan was adhered to, with a transit from Horta to Koker via Flores at FL100, the forecast altitude of the North American air close to the Azores. At Koker, we entered our operating region where we continued on our heading, and climbed to FL260 into the region of the ENVISAT overpass swath. A profiled zig-zag descent was then made along the axis of the swath, with the satellite passing overhead midway through the profile. Following this, a level run at 100ft, and a second deep profile upwards from 100ft, were made, interrupted by level runs at several different altitudes.

The first level run enroute to Koker at FL100 was noted to be slightly above the targeted pollution layer, which was actually intersected on the climb out of Horta between 8500 and 9500ft. However, the layer was occasionally sampled, as the aircraft skimmed along the upper boundary of it. The layer was characterised by elevated ozone (~80ppbv) and CO (80-100 ppbv), and was drier than the surrounding air. NO_x concentrations were also elevated when sampling the layer. Increases in sulfate aerosol were also noted in the drier polluted air.

Profile 1 sampled air between FL100 and FL260, heading towards the satellite rendezvous. Just above FL100, a thin layer of enhanced CO (110 ppbv) was intersected, as part of the target layer believed to be going onto Europe. Above FL110, a more moist layer was sampled with lower CO and ozone. The NO₂ channel failed due to low pressure at 13500ft. A broad layer of lower relative humidity (< 70%) and elevated ozone (75-90 ppbv) was sampled between FL170 and FL250. CO concentrations in this layer varied little between 65 and 75 ppbv. Elevated concentrations of acetone, acetaldehyde, RO₂ and HCHO were noted in the layer, showing possible evidence for continued 'trickle-down' processing in the aged air.

At the waypoint 40.4N, 35.4W Profile 2 was started along the axis of the ENVISAT swath in a zig-zag profile. The initial descent leg under the ENVISAT pass was made to FL155 at 1500 ft/min, which intersected the dry, ozone rich polluted layer between FL230 and FL155. A reciprocal descent was then made down to 5000 ft at 1500ft/min. A more moist layer of moderately elevated CO/ozone (70-85ppbv) was sampled, before entering a layer of ~90% relative humidity and very low ozone (15-25ppbv) below 6000ft. Descent down to 2500ft was continued at 500ft/min, followed by a reciprocal descent to 100ft. The local PBL was noted at ~1100ft, which showed a sharp increase in CO and some very low ozone concentrations (10-15 ppbv).

A series of level runs at various levels were made in an east-west orientation between ~36W and 34W. A 10-minute level run at 100ft was made, during which a ship plume was noted south of a cargo vessel, by a sharp increase in NO_x. This was followed by a

profile ascent to 3000ft, in order to sample the layer of low ozone and high relative humidity. A level run eastwards at 3000ft (R5) sampled air with reduced, but slightly higher ozone concentrations (30-45ppbv) than those observed during the profile descent. The latter part of the run entered more polluted air on the same vertical level, with CO concentrations between 80 and 90 ppbv. This layer extended vertically to ~FL80, during a profile ascent to FL110.

A level run (R6) eastwards at FL110 showed a similar air mass structure, as more polluted air was encountered towards the eastern end of the run, with the top of the polluted layer encountered at about FL120 during ascent. A level run westward at FL160 encountered a maximum of 90ppbv ozone in the polluted air mass, with associated increases in acetaldehyde and formaldehyde. These enhancements reduced as the aircraft moved westwards away from the pollution. A profile ascent to FL210 encountered a narrow polluted layer at FL200, with ozone concentrations up to ~90ppbv. This air mass was again encountered further east at a slightly higher altitude, on a level run at FL210 (R8).

A descent was then made to FL090, in order to pass through the North American layer close to the Azores at a slightly lower altitude. The upper level, dry, polluted layer was seen to extend down to FL160, below which, a more moist layer of lower ozone concentrations, anti-correlated with water and relatively invariable CO (~65 ppbv) was encountered, down to FL130. At FL120, the top of the lower level polluted layer was crossed, which lay on top of a less polluted, more moist layer down to FL90. Polluted enhancements sampled on the level run at FL90 were not as large as those intercepted in the narrow layer at FL120, and the main layer was only encountered on the final descent into Horta at ~6000ft, with CO concentrations up to ~130ppbv.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

26000

15500

5000

2500

Flight No **B.033**.....

Date 22/07/04.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:04:28 12:02:57	R2	FL100	300		O ₃ 60-80 ppbv CO 80-90 ppbv ~ level
					O ₃ / CO sharp drop ~ 11:14 UT
					crossed moderately polluted layer
					@ 9000ft. => skirted along
					top @ FL10 between 11:18-11:19
					* Return @ FL9 rather than FL11??
					11:18-11:25 CO v. flat
					~ 90 ppbv
					Slow increase to CO with decrease
					in O ₃ slow decrease to O ₃ with
					constant CO. Water/O ₃ anticorrel.
					11:29:30 increase to O ₃ / decrease
					water.
					↓
					60-70 ppbv
					small increase in CO.
					Sharp gradient 11:31. After passing
					through some concs. as in layer
					sampled on climb. → Direct over
					Flores.
					NO _x increase in drier, higher O ₃ air.
					11:15 - 11:53
					UNUS - UNUS increase in SO ₄ ²⁻
					aerosol. Lower O ₃ / moister. correlates with higher O₃.
					PTAMS - steady concs
					+ not particularly polluted.
					Re-entered polluted layer at start of profile
12:07:38 12:22:30	P1	FL100 FL260	300		Above 11000ft moister, lower O ₃ /CO layer.
					NO ₂ channel problems above 13500ft.
					Marine layer CO ~ 85 ppbv @ 13500ft
					Drier layer - correlated O ₃ /CO 16-17000ft

Aircraft Scientist's Log

3000ft
11000ft
16000ft

Flight No **B...033...**

Date **22/07/04**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Anticorrel O_3/CO dry layer 17200 Higher anticorrel HCHO
					PAN 0.3 - 0.4 ppbv
					O_3 / water anticorrel. then layer with constant CO . some evidence of trickle-down to HCHO then oxoacids? \Rightarrow evidence of elevated acetaldehyde
12:23:40	R3	FL260	290		Top layer, $CO \sim 75$ ppbv O_3 60 ppbv $\sim 90\%$ RH
12:52:17 13:00:06	P2-1	FL260 FL155	205		1500 ft/min
13:02:04 13:09:41	R2B2	FL155 FL50	025		clear layer 14500ft. CO 70 ppbv O_3 72 ppbv
13:17:27 13:27:35	P2-2	5000ft 2500ft 2000ft			v. moist low O_3 (20 ppbv) layer 7500-5000ft
					500ft/min Descending thru layer of v. low O_3 15-20 ppbv. Constant CO 75 ppbv. PBL transition \sim 1700ft??
13:29:26 13:39:23	R4	1000ft			ship plume?? H_2O 13:30
13:39:23 13:44:24	P3	1000ft -3000ft			500ft/min. N_2O 431 Precip @ 13:42:36 w 37418.2' Local PBL top \sim 11000ft line of cloud.
13:55:28	R5	3000ft			O_3 35-45 ppbv. $CO \sim 75$ ppbv
13:55:52 24	P4	3500ft -FL110			
14:07:30 14:17:30	R6	FL110			CO cat giving low O_3 \sim 14:08 CO level 75-80 ppbv. O_3 50-60 ppbv
14:19:17 14:24:35	P5	FL110 -FL160			into layer of drier higher O_3/CO then thro. low O_3/CO directly above.
					12000-13000ft \downarrow 50-60 ppbv \rightarrow \sim 60 ppbv
					Sharp gradient @ 12000ft between higher CO below. 80 \rightarrow 60 ppbv
14:24:47 14:34:20	R7	FL160			O_3 up to 80 ppbv. Acetaldehyde/HCHO increase.
14:34:20 14:39:20	P6	FL160 FL210			Enhanced O_3 layer @ \sim 20000ft 90 ppbv.

Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

Flight No B...033...

Date 22/07/2004

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Video Tapes		GPS	INU	DRS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
V8		Lat	38 31.26 N	38 31.26 N
No.		Long	28 42.98 W	28 43.80 W
Ends		Time	10:38:49	10:38:00
FFC / RFC / DFC / UFC		Status		
				HORACE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
				SATCOM <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
10 35 20								
10 44 37		TAXI		PSAP	flow off			
10 45 20		ASPs		closed				
10 51 30		T/O						
10 57 56		J-W		calc	complete			
11 27 00		Cabin temp		+26°C	24% RH			(on top of HORACE)
11 37 00		— " —		+24.6°C	21% RH			
11 39 00		Videos		recording				
11 48 00		Cabin temp		+24.1°C	21% RH			
11 58 00		SATCOM		call, CCM	→ DFL			
12 03 00		Cabin temp		+23.4°C	21% RH			
12 03 10		end of taxi						
12 19 20		Cabin temp		+21.6°C	14% RH			
12 27 35		TWC		reset				
12 28 50		TWC		source	ready			
12 35 00		Cabin temp		+23.6°C	8.4% RH			
12 42 00		— " —		+20.8°C	7.7% RH			
12 53 00		— " —		19.7°C	6.5% RH			
13 00 00		SATCOM		call, CCM	→ DFL			
13 15 00		Cabin temp		+21.1°C	22.4% RH			
13 22 00		Evm		strip	phone			
13 41 19		PSAP		flow	off			
13 46 20		PSAP		flow	on			
14 15 00		Cabin temp		+22.3°C	25% RH			
14 33 40		Cabin temp		+20.4°C	10.8% RH			
15 09 10		Cabin temp		+20.2°C	21.2% RH			
15 42 00		Cabin temp		+21.7°C	24.3% RH			
16 00 00		PSAP		flow	off			
16 01 26		LAND		HORACE				
16 05 25		GPS		fuel	posn : 38°31.26N 28 42.98 W			

FAAM 2004

16 06 00 INU fuel posn : 38°30.70N 28 41.93 W

Flight Manager's Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B033 22/7/2004

Instruments

No Radalt signal

G.E. breaker on Core Console Rear getting "sticky" and sometimes fails to make contact.

Printing of time series & XY scatter plots - scales are changed when a chart is printed.

Aircraft